

Microfinance and Women Entrepreneurs' Business Performance: The Mediating Role of Social Capital

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ABSTRACT

In the modern days, women are alleged as mutable in the global economy as businesspersons, customers and workforces. Furthermore, women have been complicated in entrepreneurship and play vigorous role as part of economic development. Women entrepreneurs are looking forward to stretch strong involvement to enhance economic progress by tumbling poverty, motivate India towards the goalmouth of fetching extraordinary revenue, maintainable and complete economy by 2020. Most literatures prorogate microfinance and social capital appear like it cannot be detached and play significant role in the entrepreneurial procedure and critical for the business presentation. Thus, the mediator role of social capital is calculated in this paper. 189 respondents were involved in the questionnaire-based study. Accordingly, this study anticipated to contribute empirical indication on the association amid microfinance on women entrepreneurs' business performance and the mediating role of social capital in the connection.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, women are termed conviction in changing the global economy as entrepreneurs, patrons and workforces. Each year, the number of women participate in workforce is cumulative and in 2018, women represent 49.5% or nearly half of the nation-wide workforce. Nowadays, microfinance program is part of chief sponsor in generating new job occasions and engendering revenue for the tenacity of cumulative social well-being and economic rank of the poor and exterminating paucity. In recent days and time, there are oodles of microfinance institution provide Government programme, NGOs and financial institutions (banks) which offer financial facilities to underprivileged people in some of the initial microfinance institutions in Chennai. The participants were selected based on their gross monthly incomes that are covered under Poverty Line Indicator (PLI) which entails poor and staunch poor households. In 1986, the microfinance scheme has been introduced with the objective of plummeting poverty by providing microcredit programme, amenities, direction, support and continuous training for the poor and inspires them to mold them into entrepreneurs. Microfinance system can be divided into a few categories which are of economic drives, non-economic commitments and retrieval. The loans/financings accessible to urban and rural poor families are supposed to be engaged in various types of legal business activities such as small businesses, manufacturing, animal farming, agriculture, fishing and other services.

2. Review of Literature

Yusuff (1995) contends that, access to financing as one of the most serious factors subsidizing to business achievement and it is also the extreme single subject faced by women entrepreneurs to initiate their business (BMS, 2013). Financial resources as in-house resources are the significant driver to the business success (Martinez et al, 2013; Siegel & Renki, 2012; Davidsson et al., 2006; Hisrich & Peters, 2002). Women mostly labelled as "risky" borrowers and less credit worthy than

men (Brush, 1992) which brand them problematic to sheltered financial capital that is critical for their business growth.

As Constantinidis et al., (2006) maintained, financial capital is the major encounters for entrepreneur, women entrepreneurs face more constraints that men entrepreneurs such as entree to capital, land and business building where the asset proprietorship is male subjugated (Roomi, 2005). As the underprivileged and women entrepreneurs do not have involvement in successively run the business, borrowing and reimbursement of financial history (Mahmood, 2009), also the amount demanded are trivial that make financial organizations diffident to reflect as it is not cost operative (Jalbert, 2000). As financial resource is recognized as major barricades for women entrepreneurs in starting and running the business (Van der Merwe, 2003; Gundry et al., 2002; Helmi, 1997), microfinance is financial services that are made accessible to those who would not generally have access to it and has been progressively renowned as a powerful tool to rejuvenate besieged economies (Richard, 2000).

Thus, the poor and women who need to be entrepreneur or engage in entrepreneurial activities need to pursue for other sources for raising capital namely microfinance. Microfinance plays as capital resource for entrepreneurs and create opportunity for entrepreneurs to generate income (Branan, 2008). Most of earlier studies settled that credit support to entrepreneurs particularly women, helps entrepreneurs performance which have best resulted in the improved income generation, output building, investment, employment and welfare of the entrepreneurs (Lakwo, 2007; Kuzilwa 2005; Peter, 2001).

Study conducted in Nigeria (Ojo, 2009; UNCDF/UNDP, 2003), Tanzania (Kuzilwa, 2005), Haiti, Kenya, Malawi (UNCDF, 2003) were originate to have positive influence on women entrepreneurs' performance. The study conducted by

Ekpe (2011) in Nigeria also supported that microfinance has positive impact on women entrepreneurs’ performance.

Although the study of fresher Norwegian firms amid men and women-owned firms by **Alsos et al. (2006)**, women entrepreneurs utilized less amount of capital than men which turn to women’s lower levels of sales and development. **Fairlie & Robb (2009)** occasioned the same on their study on study conducted by U.S Bureau of the Census, lesser levels of startup capital and previous work experience incline to lower performance of women owned firms.

Jayawardana and Aldrich (2012), in this study of retrieving microfinance provider in Australia has recognized that microfinance as an effective tool in providing all type of financial services and renowned as an actual mechanism for bringing equal opportunity for women by providing capital through compensation technologies. **Salwa et al., (2013)**

agreed, microcredit financing meaningfully lead to the success and completely affect to entrepreneurs achievement.

Daud & Yusoff (2013) elucidated that the social capital play important roles in small-sized and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by augmenting knowledge seizure, knowledge modification and knowledge transfer which could lead to modernization. In their research on 803 SMEs in Klang Valley, Malaysia showed social capital positively impacts firms performance which the relationships involve employees, customers, suppliers, alliances and partners who help to update information and knowledge. **Aldrich (1989)** reinforced that the, social capital can contribute in well-organized entree to financial capital and “the social legality might be appreciated over the high-techinvolvement of a contract in drawing the venture capital financing” (**Steier & Greenwood, 1995**).

3. Conceptual Framework

4. Hypotheses Development

- H1:** There is a significant difference between the micro finance credit and social capital
- H2:** There is a significant difference between the micro finance training and social capital
- H3:** Social capital mediates the relationship between the dimensions of micro finance and women entrepreneur business performance

5. Objectives of the Study

- To evaluate the dimensions of microfinance for women entrepreneurship
- To evaluate the effectiveness of social capital for women entrepreneurship
- To critically evaluate the effect of social capital between the effectiveness of microfinance and the outcome variable viz., women entrepreneur business performance

6. Research Methodology

A purposive sampling technique is used for the purpose of the study. This study limited to the recipients of south Chennai. The primary data is collected from 278 women members in Chennai, India through a well-structured questionnaire by face to face interview. Survey instruments were administered personally and 280 women were contacted. Out of these 280 questionnaires, 97 were rejected because of missing data or high response bias leaving an overall sample size of 183. The

survey instrument included 12 items that assessed the women empowerment. This scale is adapted from two scales developed by **Greve & Salaff, 2003; Aldrich & Zimmer, (1986)** used five latent factors which encompass factors related to micro credit and micro training using likert’s five point scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5).

7. Result and Discussion

Profile of the respondents

This section comprises of two sub sections which are the respondents profile and the result of multiple regression analysis. From 183 respondents, most of them were in the range of 41 - 50 years old (40.2%), 31 – 40 years (36%), 51- 60 years old (16.85), 61 years and above (3.3%) and 20-30 years old (2.7%). All of the respondents have formal education at least primary school (13%), while 73.9% have their secondary certificate, diploma (8.7%), college (3.3%) and only 1% of the respondents have degree and above. The result of descriptive statistics of respondents is presented in Table 1

TABLE 1: Descriptive Statistics of Respondent

Respondents’ profile	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	20 -30 years	5	2.7
	31- 40 years	68	37
	41-50 years	74	40.2
	51-60 years	31	16.8
	61 years and above	6	3.3
Educational level	Primary	24	13

	Secondary	136	73.9
	Diploma	16	8.7
	College	6	3.3
	Degree	1	.5
	Others	1	.5
Worked before	No	69	37.5
	Yes	115	62.5
Business Relevant to	Not related	67	36.4
	No	57	31
Previous worked	Yes	60	32.6

regression analysis was carried to examine the effect of microfinance on social capital as mediating variable (MV). Results indicate that the microfinance has a significant effect on social capital (B - 0.251, t=-3.402, p<0.01).

FIGURE 2: Method Used to Analyze Mediating Effect

For the analysis of multiple regressions, data cleaning and data examination in this study involved data screening followed by the data testing, which aim to meet the multivariate assumptions, satisfactorily. After screening the data, tests to meet four assumptions of multivariate analyses were conducted: normality, linearity, homoscedasticity and multicollinearity. In this study, the cut-off value for VIF is less than 11 and tolerance value of more than 0.1 and no tolerance values approaching zero (0) which specify the presence of high multicollinearity (Table 2).The dimensions of micro finance comprises of savings mobilization; credit access and vocational training has the value of 1.059. On the other hand, the social capital emerged with the value of 1.727. Hence, as deliberated in the statistical analysis, there is no violation of the assumption for this study. Therefore, the assumptions for multiple regressions are met, satisfactorily.

TABLE 2: Variance Inflation Factors (VIF)

	Tolerance	VIF
Dimensions of Microfinance	0.938	1.059
Social Capital	0.568	1.727

9. Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was carried out to determine the relationship amongst the studied variables followed by the hypotheses development. Results in Table 3 specified that the correlation coefficient (r) was high and pvalue was less than 0.01. The finding indicated that there was significant relationship between the dimensions of microfinance and social capital (r=0.503, p=0.000) followed by relationship between social capital and performance (r=0.412, p=0.000) and the relationship between social capital and microfinance (r = 0.101, p= 0.000).

TABLE 3: Intercorrelation between Variables

	Performance	Microfinance	Social Capital
Performance	1		
Dimensions of Microfinance	0.503	1	
Social Capital	0.412	0.101	1

NOTE: **P<0.05

10. Mediation Analysis

The table below shows the outcomes of hierarchical regression that examined the impact of social capital as a mediating variable in the relationship between the dimensions of microfinance and business performance. The hierarchical regression was adopted and analyzed in detailed to examine each equation as illustrated below. In equation ‘a’, the

TABLE 4: Effect of Mediating Variable on the Relationship between Microfinance and Business Performance

	B	t	Sig.
Equation a (IV to MV) Microfinance R2=0.064, F=2.404, p>0.01	-0.251	-3.402	0.01
Equation b (MV to DV) Social Capital R2=0.038, F=7.282, p<0.01	0.196	2.699	0.008
Equation c (IV to DV) Microfinance R2=0.306, F=80.310, p>0.1	0.553	8.962	0.000
Equation c' (X & M -Y) Microfinance Social Capital R2=0.427, F=67.356, p<0.01	0.644 0.359	11.071 6.169	0.000 0.000

The results showed that this study is successfully satisfied the requirements of mediating effect as described in Figure 2. The direct effect between the independent variable and the mediating variable called the path ‘a’ with the B value of -0.251, t= -3.402, p = 0.01 with the F value of 2.404. The indirect effect between mediating variable and dependent variable called the b path with the B value of 0.196, t= 2.699, p = 0.008 with the F value of 7.282. The ‘c’ path portrays the relationship of microfinance between the independent variable and dependent variable ‘B’ value of 0.553, t= 8.962, p = 0.000 with the F value of 80.310. The ‘c’ path of the micro finance and social capital variables ‘B’ value of 0.644, t= 11.071, p = 0.000; ‘B’ value of 0.359, t= 6.169, p = 0.000 with the F value of 67.356. It could be summarized that social capital partially mediates in the relationship between microfinance and women entrepreneurs business performance.

11. Conclusion & Implication

The study can be concluded based on the above discussion, that the microfinance plays a vital role in women entrepreneurs’ business as financial support. It is believed that microfinance as financial capital is the significant factors that contribute to women entrepreneurs’ business performance. Women particularly with little educational background and lack of capital essential need credit assistance which microfinance is considered as the best in improved income, output, investment, employment and welfare of the women entrepreneurs with the relevant business performance. As women entrepreneurs face many obstacles and challenges in life which in turn becomes difficult to obtain business fund,

social capital appears to be significant in the business growth. Social capital is something from a group based lending firm is understood to depiction of women entrepreneurs to social network and business opportunities to valuable information, resources and opportunity. This is seen as an important factor to business performance of women. The findings of this study supported to the fact that the microfinance has significantly connected to women entrepreneurs' business performance and the relationship is mediated by social capital. Therefore, this is the contributing factor to the existing literature of this research in this space to strengthen the entrepreneurship. This is because microfinance is the financial capital and social capital

that are playing an important role in women entrepreneurs to expand and develop their business that pave the way to improve their business performance. As far as the practical contribution is concerned, the result of this study would assistance the financial organization and government to decide and plunge into action to improvise the policies related to financial products which benefits women entrepreneurs in term of less paper work and allowance to improve their business performance.

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